

EFFECTIVENESS OF HOME-BASED LABORATORY EXPERIMENTS

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Effectiveness of Home-Based Laboratory Experiments

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Abstract

The study aimed to assess the effectiveness of home-based laboratory experiments of BSED Science and BS Biology students of Holy Name University enrolled in Genetics subject in the first semester of the Academic Year 2021-2022. This study sought to answer the effectiveness of the components of home-based laboratory experiments in terms of: alternative materials, consultations, instructional materials, references, laboratory experiment performance, and learning outcome. The study also measured the significant difference in the effectiveness between the components of home-based laboratory experiments and used the descriptive survey research design with respondents of seventeen (17) students from BSED Science and BS Biology. The frequency percentage of results and t-test were used in tabulating important information and researchers'-made survey questionnaire. Findings revealed that household kitchen items are widely used and cost less for alternative materials, Consultations are possible in terms of student-peers and student-teachers and it could also comprehend and improvise materials at home through effective instructional materials with different sources thus, students learn scientific principles. There is no significant difference in the effectiveness between the components of home-based laboratory experiments of the BSED Science and BS Biology students. Therefore, the researchers generally concluded that the effectiveness of enabling students to learn in home-based laboratory experiments depends on the flexibility, openness, and opportunity to find ways and improve home-based laboratory experiments. The researchers generally recommend promoting and continuing the ways and practices obtained throughout home-based laboratory experiments in Genetics class.

Keywords: *students, home-based laboratory experiments, descriptive*

Introduction

Science involves systematically studying the physical world, including its structures, behaviors, and the different phenomenon or events occurring. It is made possible through observations and conducting experiments to understand each circumstance and generate new knowledge and ideas. Before the COVID-19 pandemic, the conventional teacher-to-student classroom and laboratory setups were adapted. Learners engaged in laboratory experiments as a way of learning and understanding science concepts (Childhope, 2021). Experiments were conducted face to face with the teacher or a laboratory instructor and acted as facilitators for different laboratory activities involved in a given lesson or topic.

Practical exercises provided positive influence and motivation for students as they were engaged in experimental activities conducted inside the laboratory, which were made by groups to involve the students further. In the year 2020, the pandemic started, and lockdowns were introduced. Strict adherence to health protocols and social distancing was strictly implemented. This led to educational institutions in the country suspending conventional face-to-face classes (CNN Philippines, 2020). Alternative modes of learning were introduced, one of them being distance learning. Distance learning does not require interaction between instructor and students. Learners study on their own in their respective homes online or in modular.

Home-based laboratory experiments are introduced to science subjects as an alternative way of conducting experiments in educational institutions. It utilizes household materials adapted for remote learning environments and is aligned to standard learning competencies. It is a great way to enhance a student's performance in a home background setting for it utilizes the materials that they have to improve and improvise their experiments. These virtual laboratories can be used to simulate real laboratories and encourage students to engage in scientific inquiry (Oser, 2013).

Moreover, home-based experiments challenge students with basic scientific attitudes such as open and critical mindedness, objectivity, questioning attitude, tolerance of uncertainty, and respect for evidence (Darmadi et al., 2013), these attitude helps them in achieving their experiments for it shows how interested and engage they are in doing their home-based experiments. Introducing experiments, especially home-based laboratory experiments is an effective tool for students to understand scientific concepts and processes (Paul, 2021). This improves their reasoning skills and hands on skills in conducting their experiments at home. There are a lot of experimental references and sources that are accessible online, and it is easier for students to access and use them as a guide reference when conducting experiments.

The downside is that not everything is accessible and free online thus, the adaptation of home-based laboratory experiments may not help students in achieving the desired learning outcome they would acquire in the experiments. The problem in this kind of learning strategy, students will come across gaps in materials used for experiments, communication with instructor that results in failed 3 attempts in doing home-based experiments that could end up not having achievable learning competencies for the learners. As the involvement that the students had in terms of experiments before and after the pandemic could have significantly affected their interest which improved their scientific attitudes and promoted their mastery of competencies in the subject matter. This may also result in less

effort in conducting experiments because of how disinterested the learners are due to the mentioned underlying reasons (Pacifico et al., 2021).

With distance learning implemented in home-based laboratory experiments, students find alternatives in learning, understanding, and conducting the experiments at home that would be beneficial for them to understand in the comfort of their home. Therefore, the researchers are motivated to conduct this study on how effective home-based laboratory experiments are for learners. Furthermore, this study will include what benefits home-based laboratory experiments will do to the learners that would help them in learning, evaluating, and assessing the effectiveness of laboratory experiments at home. In order to fully understand the methods, there is a need to conduct this study to assess the level of how effective home-based laboratory experiments on the experiences of BSED Science and BS Biology students of Holy Name University enrolled in Genetics subject in the first semester of the Academic Year 2021-2022.

Research Questions

The study aimed to assess the effectiveness of home-based laboratory experiments of BSED Science and BS Biology students of Holy Name University enrolled in Genetics subject in the first semester of the Academic Year 2021-2022. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the effectiveness of home-based laboratory experiments in terms of:
 - 1.1. alternative materials;
 - 1.2. consultations;
 - 1.3. instructional materials;
 - 1.4. references;
 - 1.5. laboratory experiment performance; and
 - 1.6. learning outcome?
2. Is there a significant difference between the BSED Science and BS Biology students in terms of the effectiveness of home-based laboratory experiments in their Genetics subject?

Methodology

Respondents

The target respondents of the study were the BSED Science and BS Biology students enrolled in Genetics subject class of Holy Name University in the first semester of academic year 2021-2022. The researchers used total population sampling since they focused on a specific subject in assessing the effectiveness of home-based laboratory experiments. In relation to this, 100% of the respective student's programs were the respondents. Thus, the total number of respondents was seventeen (17) students.

Due to the small number of students enrolled in the genetics subject class, the researchers only used 17 respondents. Selecting only one subject to be evaluated on how effective the home-based laboratory experiments are, so that the researchers may only focus on a single course subject that avoids a change in stimuli. Several courses that were considered for inclusion had dubious data outcomes. As a result, the researchers reasoned that one subject with 17 respondents was already adequate and sufficient for the research because only a limited group of students was enrolled in laboratory courses that involved home-based experiments.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Academic Year 2021-2022 (First semester)</i>		
<i>Student's course program</i>	<i>Population of Students</i>	<i>Sample respondents</i>
A BSED Science	8	8
B BS Biology	9	9
Total	17	17

Instrument

The instrument used was a researcher-made questionnaire to gather the needed data. The questionnaire was drawn out based on the researcher-made questionnaire from Experimental Activities in The Laboratory of Analytical Chemistry Under an Inquiry Approach, Arias et al. (2014).

In the preparation of the instrument, the researchers considered the requirements in designing a good data collection instrument. For instance, the researchers toned down statements describing the situations or issues about accommodating the respondents' knowledge preparedness. The researchers provided closed-ended options to accommodate free formatted views related to the topics or issues. In this way, the instrument was authorized to obtain valid responses from the students.

The data gathered in this study was created through Google Forms and sent to the respondents through their respective HNU emails. The respondent's participation in the survey was voluntary. Furthermore, the data gathered in this study depends on the respondents' answers, which were gauged through questionnaires. The answering of the survey questionnaire only took about 5-10 minutes. After the thesis proposal and ERB clearance was obtained, pilot testing was done to test the researcher-made questionnaire's credibility.

Part I of the survey questionnaire contains the profile of the respondents, which indicates the respondent's name (optional) and course. Furthermore, part II of the survey questionnaire covers the alternative materials, consultation, instructional materials, references, laboratory experiment performance and learning outcome where the researchers determined the effectiveness of home-based laboratory experiments during the pandemic.

For the researchers, this is how the scale is described but it is not placed in the google form questionnaire:

Yes - The students who have taken up the subject Genetics and answered

the survey questionnaire agreed that he/she learned throughout home-based laboratory experiment in Genetics subject because of using the right and alternative materials, the proper consultation with the teacher, and fellow students, understandable instructional materials that guide the students throughout the experiment, finding the right references, how they perform well their laboratory experiments and how this performance affect the expected learning outcome. This quantitative description means that the students fully agree with the statement in each item.

No - The students who have taken up the subject Genetics and answered

the survey questionnaire, disagreed that he/she did not learned throughout the home- based laboratory experiment the Genetics subject stated in each item of the questionnaire. This quantitative description means that the students fully disagree with the statement in each item.

Procedure

Data Gathering. The researchers wrote a letter to the Registrar's Office of HNU and the researchers formally asked permission to get the list of the total population of BSED Science and BS Biology students of Holy Name University enrolled in Genetics subject in the first semester of academic year 2020-2021. The researchers also asked permission to conduct a survey from the Deans for the entire College of Education and the College of Arts and Sciences through writing a formal letter with the signature of the thesis leader and thesis adviser. After the letter has been approved from the Deans, another letter was sent to the BSED Science and BS Biology students for informed consent and to further request participation in answering the survey questionnaires with all sincerity and honesty. This letter was sent to the total population of BSED Science and BS Biology respondents enrolled in Genetics subject class in the first semester of the academic year 2021-2022 consisting of eight (8) respondents from the BSED Science degree program and nine (9) respondents from BS Biology degree program which has a total of seventeen (17) respondents.

The data gathered in this study was created through Google Forms and sent to the respondents through their respective HNU emails. Furthermore, the data gathered in this study depends on the respondents' answers, which were gauged through questionnaires. Answering the survey questionnaire only took about 5-10 minutes.

After the research process has been successfully conducted, the researchers retrieved the survey questionnaires and made the template for the summary of responses tally. Right after the retrieval of the research instrument, the researchers with the help of the statistician tabulated and collated the data. Quantitative data processing was determined to arrive at a scientific analysis and interpretation of the results.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers followed the steps in gathering data after the researchers obtained Ethical Research Board (ERB) clearance. In this study, no conflicts of interest were discovered. And rest assured that the researchers who were also BSED Science students were excluded from the survey to avoid bias. Furthermore, the researchers guaranteed that each respondent should answer with integrity and honesty, informing the researchers' classmates that they must strictly adhere to ethical standards. The respondents were not given any positive reward for answering the researchers' questions. The names and other information provided by the respondents were optional when collecting data and all of the information gathered was appreciated and cherished. The respondents were provided an informed consent form as a form of agreement between the researchers and the respondents, and all respondents were not required to supply all of the information requested by the researchers. The researchers highly encouraged the respondents to participate in the study due to the limited number of BSED Science and BS Biology students enrolled in the Genetics subject class in the first semester of academic year 2021-2022. Moreover, there was no risk during the entire research process, for the respondents were provided with an informed consent form as a method of agreement between the researchers and the respondents. All respondents were required to supply only some of the information requested by the researchers.

The researchers were confident that the exchange of personal information and survey answers from the respondents would only be used for the study and not for further use. In connection with this, the researchers ensured that this study would not cause any harm or expose the respondents' vulnerabilities because it would all be based on the respondent's self-assessment on assessing effectiveness of home-based laboratory experiments.

Furthermore, not only the researchers and participants benefit from this study, but so the students, parents, the teachers, and it will serve as a reference for future studies. The researchers assured that for the sake of safety and privacy, as well as to avoid problematic situations, the vulnerability of all respondents was strictly forbidden from any dissemination.

Results and Discussion

In this section, the researchers presents the descriptive and inferential results of the study. Data gathered are organized by tabulating important information based on computation. Textual discussion followed every table of numerical figures to give meaning to the values presented.

Table 2. *Alternative Materials*

<i>Indicator/s</i>	<i>Yes</i>		<i>No</i>	
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>frequency</i>	<i>%</i>
In performing the laboratory experiment in genetics class, I was able to learn because of;				
1. the availability of alternative materials at home.	13	76.47	4	23.53
2. the modification I made to the available materials at home that I used in my laboratory experiments.	12	70.59	5	29.41
3. the availability of alternative materials that can be bought in the local market (if there are no other alternatives that can be found at home).	14	82.35	3	17.65
4. the freedom of choosing the materials to accomplish the laboratory experiments (quality-wise).	14	82.35	3	17.65
5. affordable cost of materials which I can choose freely.	14	82.35	3	17.65
Total	67	78.82	18	21.18

The effectiveness of home-based laboratory experiments in terms of alternative materials. The researchers revealed that the availability of alternative materials at home, such as household kitchen items, was widely used to complete a particular experiment in the students' Genetics subject. It also allows the students to choose efficient and less costly alternative materials available in their area. On the other hand, the table reveals that there where students who were having difficulties in modifying any alternative materials present in the students' respective areas.

Table 3. *Consultations*

<i>Indicator/s</i>	<i>Yes</i>		<i>No</i>	
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>frequency</i>	<i>%</i>
In performing the laboratory experiment in genetics class, I was able to learn because;				
Student-Teacher Consultations				
1. I can easily contact my laboratory instructor with questions and clarifications about the laboratory experiment (through his email address, Facebook account, and phone number to contact the instructor).	15	88.24	2	11.76
2. there are immediate responses or replies from my laboratory instructor (through private comment feedback in google classroom, messenger reply).	13	76.47	4	23.53
3. my laboratory instructor always engages with his students, especially during his subject hours.	14	82.35	3	17.65
Total	42	82.35	9	17.65
Student-Peers Consultations				
4. I can easily approach my classmates if there are grouped experiments or questions I don't fully understand, and I seek help from them.	15	88.24	2	11.76
5. there is collaborative work with my classmates and information sharing on group activities and projects (conveying messages).	16	94.12	1	5.88
6. my relationship with them in working on the given experiment enhances my social skills.	17	100	0	0
Total	48	94.12	3	5.88

The effectiveness of home-based laboratory experiments in terms of consultations. The data reveals that in performing home-based laboratory experiments in a genetics course, majority of the students were able to have consultation in terms of student-peers and student-teachers' consultation. The researchers found out that majority of students can contact and ask for consultations with their teachers. On the other hand, students-peers consultation helps the students to socialize, are comfortable with each other, and their classmate collaborates with one another. On the contrary, the table also reveals that some students are having difficulty in communicating with their laboratory instructor. While in terms of peer consultations, some students were having difficulty in approaching other students.

The effectiveness of home-based laboratory experiments in terms of instructional materials. In performing home-based laboratory experiments in the Genetics course, most students could use their instructors' given laboratory guidelines and instructional materials efficiently. The data indicates that students could comprehend, follow, and improvise their materials at home because of effective instructional materials. On the contrary, some students having difficulty in understanding the sequence of instructional materials given by the laboratory instructor.

Table 4. *Instructional Materials*

<i>Indicator/s</i>	<i>Yes</i>		<i>No</i>	
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>frequency</i>	<i>%</i>
In performing the laboratory experiment in genetics class, I was able to learn because of;				
1. the sequence of the instructional material's procedure is understandable and easy to perform.	12	70.58	5	29.41
2. the instructional materials' content was completely organized and provided according to the lesson's learning objectives.	15	88.23	2	11.76
3. I have followed appropriately the instructional materials given by the laboratory instructor.	16	94.11	1	5.88
4. the instructional materials help me succeed in accomplishing my laboratory experiments.	16	94.11	1	5.88
5. of understandable instructional materials; I was satisfied with the outcome of my experiment and eventually praised by my teacher for finishing my work effectively.	14	82.35	3	5.88
Total	73	85.87	12	11.76

Table 5. *References*

<i>Indicator/s</i>	<i>Yes</i>		<i>No</i>	
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>frequency</i>	<i>%</i>
In performing the laboratory experiment in genetics class, I was able to learn because;				
1. I found suitable sources to base my laboratory experiments on if I needed help understanding the instructional materials given by the laboratory instructor.	11	64.70	6	35.30
2. I scanned some textbooks and visited search engines that effectively accomplished my laboratory experiments.	14	82.40	3	17.70
3. I scanned some textbooks and visited search engines that are helpful to my laboratory experiments, significantly enhancing my way of performing the experiments.	15	88.24	2	11.80
4. I learned so much by scanning textbooks and visiting search engines because many references support my experiment.	12	70.60	5	29.41
5. I obtained knowledge about the searches I have made in terms of scientific principles in the laboratory experiment, and it influenced my way of solving practical problems.	12	70.60	5	29.41
Total	64	75.31	21	24.72

The effectiveness of home-based laboratory experiments in terms of reference. The researchers revealed that, majority of the students could understand the experiment more in searching different references or sources. The sources, such as textbooks and search engines used by the students to complete the task they gave, were practical and useful. On the other hand, some students are having difficulty finding suitable sources to base their home based laboratory experiments.

Table 6. *Laboratory Experiment Performance*

<i>Indicator/s</i>	<i>Yes</i>		<i>No</i>	
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>frequency</i>	<i>%</i>
In performing the laboratory experiment in genetics class, I was able to learn because;				
1. home-based laboratory experiments in genetics were easier to do than campus- based experiments, and I enjoyed the home-based laboratory experiments more.	4	23.53	13	76.47
2. I confidently conducted the experiments in genetics effectively with the proper use of alternative materials and following the instructional materials given.	11	64.71	6	35.29
3. I can easily formulate the procedures while performing laboratory experiments in genetics, and if it is successful, it inspires me to complete the next experiment well.	13	76.47	4	23.53
4. for each experiment in genetics, I understood the concept of specific experiments.	14	82.35	3	17.65
5. I actively looked for ways to improve my genetics experiments, and I'm open to new possibilities to enhance my practice of performing the experiments.	15	88.24	2	11.76
Total	57	67.06	28	32.94

The effectiveness of home-based laboratory experiments in terms of laboratory experiment performance. The researchers revealed that majority of the students were able to look for ways to improve their laboratory experiments and positively accept the results. On the contrary, some students are having difficulty performing their experiments at home and home-based laboratory experiment in genetics class was more challenging, and they enjoyed the campus-based laboratory experiment more.

The effectiveness of home-based laboratory experiments in terms of learning outcome. The researchers revealed that majority of the students could learn the scientific principles in laboratory experiments, specifically in their genetics course. Which means that the alternative materials made by the students, consultations from their laboratory teachers and classmates, instructional materials given by the instructor, and finding the right references to support their laboratory experiment performance were why students learned scientific principles. On the other hand, some laboratory experiments couldn't improve the student's laboratory skill and their knowledge were unchanged.

Table 7. *Learning Outcome*

<i>Indicator/s</i>	<i>Yes</i>		<i>No</i>	
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>frequency</i>	<i>%</i>
In performing the laboratory experiment in genetics class, I was able to learn because;				
1. I learned the scientific principles in laboratory experiments, specifically in my genetics course.	15	88.24	2	11.76
2. It improved the laboratory skills that I had already acquired before the home-based laboratory set-up.	11	64.71	6	35.29
3. It helped me better understand theoretical and critical concepts that will guide me throughout my life journey.	14	82.35	3	17.65
4. It influenced my way of solving scientific research problems, which will be useful in handling and encountering other people in the future.	14	82.35	3	17.65
5. It allowed me to improve my ability to design procedures; and to collect, analyze and interpret data which would be very useful for my profession in the future.	14	82.35	3	17.65
Total	68	80	17	20

Table 7. *Significant Difference of Effectiveness of Home-based Laboratory Experiments in Genetics Class*

	<i>Course</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error Mean</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Alternative Materials	BS Bio	.7333	.37417	.12472	0.705	0.492	Accept Ho
	BSED Scie	.8500	.29761	.10522			
Consultations	BS Bio	.9256	.16920	.05640	1.105	0.286	Accept Ho
	BSED Scie	.8325	.17774	.06284			
Instructional Materials	BS Bio	.8222	.18559	.06186	0.803	0.434	Accept Ho
	BSED Scie	.9000	.21381	.07559			
References	BS Bio	.7111	.44845	.14948	0.490	0.631	Accept Ho
	BSED Scie	.8000	.26186	.09258			
Laboratory Experiment Performance	BS Bio	.6667	.28284	.09428	0.055	0.957	Accept Ho
	BSED Scie	.6750	.33700	.11915			
Learning Outcome	BS Bio	.8444	.32830	.10943	0.527	0.606	Accept Ho
	BSED Scie	.7500	.41057	.14516			

The significant difference of effectiveness of home-based laboratory experiments in genetics class. Based on the gathered data, there is no significant difference between BSED Science and BS Biology students in terms of effectiveness of home-based laboratory experiments in their Genetics class. All of the six (6) components presented from alternative materials down to learning outcome indicates that mentioned components have a p-value greater than 0.05 alpha resulting in the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This means that both degree programs accepts the null hypothesis which specifies that students from BSED Science and BS Biology have the same ways and practices in making their home-based laboratory experiments.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the study concluded that household kitchen items are widely used to complete a particular experiment in the students' genetics subject due to their cost-effectiveness. Proper consultations with teachers and peers significantly improve the conduct of home-based laboratory experiments by providing and sharing the necessary information for the effective conduct of home-based experiments. Students efficiently utilized laboratory guidelines and instructions to improvise the available alternative materials. The references provided by textbooks and search engines to the students are effective in allowing the students to help them comprehend and understand the experiment. Most students disagreed that genetics home-based laboratory experiments are much more manageable than on-campus experimentation. The study still revealed that upon performing home-based laboratory experiments in the genetics course, most students could learn the scientific principles in laboratory experiments, specifically in their genetics course. Overall, the flexibility, openness, and opportunity of finding ways to improve home-based laboratory experiments could offset all of the challenges in the conduct of home-based laboratory experiments.

In view of the findings, the following recommendations are offered:

To strengthen home-based laboratory experiments, providing "At-Home Lab Kit" is what the researchers recommend. Home-based laboratory experiments will be successful and made possible by sending students an "At-Home Lab Kit" from the university. The components of which are simple in design. The one that is responsible for the distribution and the selection of the content of the lab kits are on the hands of the laboratory instructors. In terms of sending those lab kits to students, it is the responsibility of each laboratory departments to choose the appropriate logistics partner.

To increase engagement between student and teacher, teachers should include online consultation through virtual meetings and chats

if possible such as giving consultation days and hours for that subject (e.g., every F at 4:00 to 5:00 pm for virtual meeting).

To have an effective instructional material, laboratory instructors should always verify and improve the contents of the instructional materials and other textbooks and provide understandable procedures and clear instructions so that the student would comprehend and execute their experiments well.

To strengthen instructional materials that guide the students throughout their experiments at home, laboratory instructors should hand out experiment guidelines that fit the grade level's performance rather than instructing complex guidelines and materials for the students to follow, perform, and improvise.

In preparatory for home-base laboratory experiments, instructors should provide activities/group activities base on the different scientific theories that engages, motivates, and assists students in utilizing their prior knowledge to their laboratory experiments.

For future researchers, Further investigation is recommended to develop the performance of home-based laboratory experiments as an alternative learning in today's generation.

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